

Session Report: Hands-On Session on the Methods Hub

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Abstract

The Methods Hub is an open-access platform designed to support social science researchers in discovering, accessing, understanding, and applying computational methods. This session introduces the Methods Hub as a portal for computational methods and demonstrates its core functionalities, guiding participants through the process of finding suitable methods, accessing them, and understanding their purpose. The session also highlights the utility of tutorials, serving as a step-by-step guide to demonstrate the application of a method for a concrete task. As an interactive session, the participants choose from predefined use case scenarios to collaboratively explore the platform, search methods, find suitable method and execute it interactively. The participants understood the purpose of the methods, their inputs and outputs from their respective homepages, and discussed them in relation to the use cases. The participants shared their feedback on the activity and collaborated in shaping ideas for the future of Methods Hub. The participants pointed pains in content exploration, more visibility and credit for the content developers and tutorials that assist educators.

1. Methods Hub

The Methods Hub is an online platform which aims at supporting social scientists in leveraging computational methods to work with huge amount of data available on social media and related platforms for their research questions Bleier et al. (2025). Computational methods are required to develop pipelines that retrieve, process, and analyze large data. Access to reproducible computational methods is crucial. However, finding, accessing, understanding, reusing, and applying computational methods to domain-specific datasets is still a challenge that significantly impacts research in computational social science, hindering fast discoveries and reproducibility. A dedicated platform for sharing and searching reusable methods targeting social sciences does not exist, while methods and learning materials are scattered across individual, institutional, or general sharing portals.

The Methods Hub aims to fill this gap by targeting social scientists who want to: (1) find reusable state-of-the-art computational methods that are relevant for social science research, (2) learn about using these methods via tutorials, and contribute their own methods and tutorials to foster visibility and citations. Additionally, Methods Hub facilitates reproducible analysis through interactive execution environment, enabling users to directly apply methods, adapt and test them in their research context.

The target group for Methods Hub consists of all social scientists interested in analyzing digital data, such as social media data. This includes researchers interested in filtering and processing large data, learning more about methods via tutorials, and finding relevant methods to modify according to their research questions on their own computer or through online execution back-ends. The methods directly applicable for analyzing GESIS sensitive data might also be useful for researchers. Methods Hub is also a platform for method developers with computer science or computational social science background to share their latest Artificial intelligence/Machine learning methods with the community. As content providers, they can promote, advertise their tools; as well as connect their tools to social science analysis tools e.g., connecting claims detection feeds into network analysis.

The Methods Hub offers methods addressing diverse tasks in social science research. The methods and their tutorials are categorized into (1) data collection and retrieval methods (e.g., web scraping, web tracking, API data extraction, sensor data acquisition), (2) data preprocessing methods (e.g., data cleaning, text processing, data encryption, data anonymization, feature engineering, normalization

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and data transformation), (3) data mining methods (e.g., text mining, graph mining, data classification, data clustering, data enrichment, large language models), (3) analysis methods (e.g., social network analysis, spatial analysis, temporal analysis, time-series analysis, pattern recognition), (4) visualization methods (e.g., network visualization, tabular data visualization). Following open science principles, the content hosted there is open source, released under an open license, and implemented in open source programming languages, including but not limited to R, and Python. The content on the Methods Hub is carefully curated and reviewed to ensure adherence to expert-designed reproducibility and reusability guidelines Momeni et al. (2025). The portal encourages the use of best practices through templates, which help developers to develop and submit new content.

2. Interactive Execution for Reproducibility

Reproducibility is a cornerstone of scientific research, and interactive execution plays a vital role in making computational research transparent, accessible, and verifiable. Traditional approaches to sharing code and results often involve static artifacts such as scripts, datasets, or PDF files, which can be difficult to reproduce due to environment mismatches or missing dependencies.

The Methods Hub uses MyBinder¹ to ensure the reproducibility of the content. Mybinder is a community-run cloud service offering reproducible interactive computing environments based on Docker and repo2docker Saju et al. (2025). It launches live sessions of notebooks or scripts directly from one's web browser, based on the content hosted in a Git repository. Content hosted on the Methods Hub must have configuration files for repo2docker², which automatically configure a reproducible computational environment for rendering the content and interactive execution. Not only the content is automatically reproducible, users can also use the content directly from within Methods Hub by launching an interactive execution environment on their web browser.

3. Collaborative Activity

The collaborative activity in the session comprises of 2 or 3 groups working together on a use case of their choice:

- **Use Case 1:** Josh has a dataset of a few hundred social media posts on climate change. He wants to use a method to extract useful social media entities from the posts to help with further analysis.
- **Use Case 2:** Sarah has a few hundred blog posts, each discussing a movie's plot. She wants to use a method to extract the most representative keywords for each post.
- **Use Case 3:** Shah has downloaded a dataset of social media posts and wants to sample the posts that are highly relevant to his keywords of interest.

The participants are given the following three tasks to perform for their use case. The tasks are aligned in a sequence to reproduce the results of a published method.

- **Task 0:** Which step in the research pipeline does the method belong to?
- **Task 1:** Search for/find a suitable method for the use case
- **Task 2:** Interactively execute the method and explore results

4. Participant Demographics

The session is attended by three participants where each participant decide to work on each use case. It introductory session helped to navigate the portal, while the session organizers assisted with the tasks and responded to queries.

¹<https://mybinder.org/>

²for example, *requirements.txt* defining Python dependencies. More information: <https://repo2docker.readthedocs.io/en/latest/configuration/>

Variable	Value
Gender	2 male, 1 female
Career stage	1 PhD, 1 PhD student, 1 early-career research
Disciplinary background	Political science, sociology, public health, social work, media studies
Geographic spread	Belgium (2), eastern europe/Nordic/EU (1)

Table 1

Participant demographics

5. Participants Feedback

The participants shared the following feedback on their experience of exploring the Methods Hub platform and executing their tasks for the chosen use case.

- “Very interesting to learn about the methods provided by GESIS. It’s quite useful!” (PhD, Political Science/Sociology, Belgium)
- “Quite easy to understand how it works. The site is quite intuitive.” (PhD student, Public Health, Belgium)
- “This is great. I would be happy to know it earlier and looking forward to using it in my work with students. Will learn myself and teach students to use it.” (Early-career researcher, Political Science/Social Work, Eastern Europe/Nordic/EU)

In summary, the participants found the platform intuitive, useful for research, and promising as a teaching tool.

6. Insights from Interactive Discussion (Miro Board)

Participants reflected on their roles as users, developers, and educators, and shared what they gain from methods, which pains they experience, and what tasks they try to accomplish. They also suggested ways the Methods Hub could address these needs.

6.1. User

Gains: appreciate having an overview of available methods and the ability to combine them to solve complex problems.

Pains: face challenges due to limited IT skills, difficulties finding the right method, and uncertainty about comparing methods (“why is one better than another?”).

Jobs: conduct data analysis efficiently and with confidence.

6.2. Developer

Gains: see the Methods Hub as a space to share their expertise and receive recognition.

Pains: not explicitly raised, but implied issues of visibility and support burden could be relevant.

6.3. Educator

Gains: value structured resources that can be adapted for teaching.

Pains: struggle with low student motivation, frequent “for what?” questions about why a method matters, and fear of mathematics among students.

Jobs: select appropriate methods and adapt them to students’ needs.

6.4. Suggestions for Methods Hub (Value Proposition)

Curated Playlists: One participant suggested creating playlists of methods tailored to particular student groups or learning paths. This would help in motivating students and providing clear entry points.

Infrastructure Support: one comment humorously asked for “lots of GPU for free,” highlighting the underlying demand for accessible computational resources when teaching or applying methods.

7. Key Takeaways

The Miro discussion confirmed that different stakeholder groups have different needs:

- Users want better discovery and clarity.
- Educators want curated and motivating teaching resources.
- Developers want visibility and credit.

The Methods Hub can strengthen its value proposition by aligning features, like playlists, tutorials, and improved search, to directly address these pains and create tangible gains.

8. Acknowledgements

Arnim Bleier³ and Lorraine Saju⁴

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³<https://github.com/taimoorkhan-nlp/Reproducibility-ICWSM25>

⁴<https://github.com/taimoorkhan-nlp/r2cass-icwsm>